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Perceptions of Inquiry-based Learning in Higher Education: A Case Study from North Macedonia

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Abstract

Inquiry-based learning (IBL) is a learner-centred approach based on using students' questions to facilitate learning. This approach is based on constructivist philosophy, particularly the work of Piaget, Dewey and Vygostky. Because it is suitable for developing students' critical thinking skills, modern educational methodologists call for its wider use in the classroom, not only in language teaching but also in other disciplines. The present study aims to explore teachers' and students' perceptions and classroom experiences of IBL in the EFL classroom at tertiary level. The research context is the South East European University (SEEU) in Tetovo, North Macedonia. The study, which uses two instruments, a survey and an interview for data collection, found that IBL has several benefits, including the development of communication skills, collaboration among students, critical thinking and active learning.

Keywords: Inquiry-based learning, tertiary level, language learning, teachers and students' perceptions

1 Introduction

With the inclusion of Artificial Intelligence in education, learners and teachers are exposed to unlimited resources and tools for learning and teaching. The education system in North Macedonia is going through tremendous changes in all levels of education. Not leaving any child behind is one of the core issues of the national curriculum and universities must prepare future teachers to respond to the diversity and differentiation that they will face in the future. One of the best ways to achieve these goals is using modern teaching methods and approaches which put the learner in the centre of learning. An important current trend in teaching EFL which engages learners a lot and promotes active learning is inquiry-based learning.

Inquiry-based learning is a pedagogical approach which has its roots in the 1960s when discovery learning, as opposed to traditional teaching methods such as the Grammar-Translation Method, began to be used (Brunner 1961). Based on Dewey's pedagogy of experiential learning, inquiry is conducted in a way that is based on the main principles that students should engage with the content, ask questions in class and work together to find solutions to different learning problems. Additionally, learners are expected to construct knowledge by themselves and based on experiences.

The present study focuses on teachers' and students' perceptions and experiences with inquiry-based learning at a tertiary level of education, i.e. at the South East

European University (SEEU) in North Macedonia. The institutions in this country strive to move away from traditional teaching methods, used until recently, to modern teaching methods including technology such as Mobile-assisted language learning, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, Online quizzes, Podcasts and AI in education. The utilisation of modern technology enhances inquiry-based learning because technology creates environments that engage learners in self-learning and increases their autonomy.

Indeed, there is a growing recognition of the importance of preparing learners for the demands of 21st-century education, which emphasises critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity. Inquiry-based learning plays a crucial role in promoting these skills by engaging students in activities that require them to think critically, analyse information, and generate creative solutions to real-world problems.

At the South East European University, various learning activities are implemented to enhance students' learning experiences. These activities include classroom debates, research papers, projects, group work, class reflections, online quizzes, all of which provide opportunities for students to explore complex issues, collaborate with their peers, and apply their knowledge in practical contexts. No doubt, teachers play a pivotal role in shaping students' learning experiences and helping them develop the skills necessary for success in the 21st century. By understanding teachers' perspectives on inquiry-based learning, this study aims to provide insights into how best to support educators in implementing effective teaching approaches and promoting student learning and achievement.

2 Basic Aspects of Inquiry-based Learning

Inquiry-based learning is a contemporary approach based on constructivist principles that place the learner at the centre of learning. The main principles of this approach are *problem-solving*, *investigations* and *questions*:

Inquiry-based teaching has often focused on its application in science and maths education, but the approach is equally well-suited to the teaching of the humanities'. (Sweetland 2008: 1)

Furthermore, the role of the teacher in an inquiry-based classroom is quite different from that of a teacher in a conventional classroom. Instead of providing direct instruction to students, teachers help students generate their own content-related questions and guide the investigation that follows (ibid.). The role of the teacher is very important in this process because his or her task is to lead and facilitate learning.

Regarding this issue, Pappes (2014) summarises four different forms of inquiries used in this approach:

- *Confirmation inquiry*: This is a question or method given to learners with known results at the end. This type of inquiry offers learners an opportunity to reinforce ideas which require the practice of investigative skills.
- *Structured inquiry*: The learner is given a question or a method by which to

arrive at the end result. The aim is to provide explanations for the evidence provided during a confirmation inquiry.

- *Guided inquiry*: Learners only get the question, and the idea is to design a method of investigating the question itself.
- *Open inquiry*: Learners form their questions, design the methods of investigation, conduct their inquiry and present the results.

Laursen & Rasmussen (2019) summarise four pillars of inquiry-based learning, which include student engagement with meaningful tasks, student collaboration, teacher inquiry, student thinking, and the promotion of equity in the design of facilitative choices by teachers. Alfieri et al. (2011: 3) believe that inquiry-based learning has the advantage of allowing students to interact with materials and models, manipulate variables, explore phenomena and attempt to apply principles, and provides them with opportunities to notice patterns, discover their underlying causalities and learn in ways that appear more robust. When it comes to the methodology of inquiry-based teaching, it is based on the 5E model (*engage, explore, explain, evaluate, and elaborate*). This model is flexible, and it offers best teaching practices (Bybee 2009). The 5E model is also based on constructivism and supports students' learning through experience:

Phase	Summary
Engagement	The teacher or a curriculum task accesses the learners' prior knowledge and helps them become engaged in a new concept through the use of short activities that promote curiosity and elicit prior knowledge. The activity should make connections between past and present learning experiences, expose prior conceptions, and organize students' thinking toward the learning outcomes of current activities.
Exploration	Exploration experiences provide students with a common base of activities within which current concepts (i.e., misconceptions); processes, and skills are identified and conceptual change is facilitated. Learners may complete lab activities that help them use prior knowledge to generate new ideas, explore questions and possibilities, and design and conduct a preliminary investigation.
Explanation	The explanation phase focuses students' attention on a particular aspect of their engagement and exploration experiences and provides opportunities to demonstrate their conceptual understanding, process skills, or behaviors. This phase also provides opportunities for teachers to directly introduce a concept, process, or skill.
Elaboration	Teachers challenge and extend students' conceptual understanding and skills. Through new experiences, students develop deeper and broader understanding, more information, and adequate skills. Students apply their understanding of the concept by conducting additional activities

Evaluation	The evaluation phase encourages students to assess their understanding and abilities and provides opportunities for teachers to evaluate student progress toward achieving the educational objectives.
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Table 1: 5 E Model (Bybee et.al.2006: 2)

Williams (2019) suggests that the 5E model for instruction can be used as a flexible one that can be very useful for curriculum development, instructors, and other educators based on constructivism and best teaching practices. In 2023, Zusy introduced a model of instruction that prioritises engaging students in the classroom to foster knowledge acquisition through phased lessons. This innovative approach is characterised by inquiry-based learning, which fundamentally shifts the dynamic of education from passive reception to active discovery. Including inquiry as a teaching method, students are given the opportunity to explore information themselves, rather than simply receiving it through traditional lecturing or instruction.

Furthermore, the main benefits of inquiry-based learning are that it enhances critical thinking, comprehension and communication skills; it helps students to explore different topics; it supports language learning and ideally makes students love learning; it is useful for different types of classrooms and promotes diversity and differentiation in the classroom (Crocket 2019). Nonetheless, there are three main disadvantages of inquiry-based learning, which Gutierrez (2018) lists. These include concerns about decreased performance in standardised testing; the risk of overlooking important issues if too much time is devoted to student inquiries, and student discomfort with the level of participation required; and potential unpreparedness of teachers to effectively facilitate inquiry-based lessons. These reflections show that implementing inquiry-based learning is not an easy task for teachers as there exist several obstacles which need to be overcome.

Recently, several studies have looked at the effectiveness of the inquiry-based method in ELT in different contexts.

Stepanechko & Kozub (2022) conducted a quantitative survey to collect data from 76 students who were enrolled in a specialised program in cybernetics and IT. The participants' age ranged from 17-18 years old. The study aimed to present the implementation of the inquiry-based method in English language classes and to determine if this method is effective to develop students' speaking skills. The activities used were those that encouraged collaboration between students and other learning materials, increased learners' intrinsic motivation and promoted critical thinking. The teacher's sole role was that of a facilitator who organises students' learning and fosters their critical thinking and engagement in learning. The findings showed that there were many benefits of inquiry-based learning such as the development of students' curiosity, inspiration of deep learning and cognition as well as the increase of motivation and their overall learning achievements.

Gholam (2017) employed a mixed approach; the research questions were related to some challenges of implementing inquiry-based learning and to find out the reasons why student teachers favour using it in the classroom. Eight participants, all students, completed the survey. The results revealed that the participants were of the

opinion that the school system was an obstacle for the implementation of inquiry-based learning in the classroom. The study recommended that inquiry-based learning should be used at all levels of schooling, starting in the early stages of development. According to the study, the integration of inquiry-based learning into the school curriculum can enhance interaction and students' questioning techniques.

In conclusion, the implementation of inquiry-based learning in EFL teaching and learning has its advantages, but also presents considerable challenges.

3 Methodology

The present study was conducted with the aim of exploring the potential of inquiry-based learning at the tertiary level in SEEU, North Macedonia. It was considered to be a pioneering project because none of the studies previously dealt with this issue in the given research context. By examining teachers' perceptions, students' attitudes and experiences, and the perceived benefits of inquiry-based learning, the study aimed to provide insights into the effectiveness and potential challenges of implementing this approach in EFL instruction at the tertiary level.

The study aimed to address the following research questions:

- Q1: What are teachers' perceptions of the inquiry-based approach at the tertiary level of education?
- Q2: What are students' attitudes and experiences with inquiry-based learning in their classroom?
- Q3: What are the benefits of implementing inquiry-based learning in the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom?

These research questions were designed to explore the perspectives of both teachers and students regarding inquiry-based learning in the tertiary education context, particularly focusing on the EFL classroom.

The institution in which the present study was carried out is the South East European University (SEEU) located in Tetovo, North Macedonia. The study was conducted at the Faculty of Languages, Cultures and Communication, one of the seven faculties of this university. Students enrolled on the English Language and Literature major, BA programme. After graduation, the majority of them became EFL teachers; therefore, training them in using modern approaches is crucial for their success in their future teaching career. Additionally, the SEEU is a multilingual University which promotes learner-centred education, combines the best possible inquiry-based learning practices and trains its staff continuously. It is now regarded as a model for multi-ethnic, multi-lingual higher education in South East Europe.

The present study employed two research instruments: a teacher survey and student interviews. The teacher survey contained two parts: 1) perceptions of inquiry-based

teaching and 2) usefulness of inquiry-based instruction. According to Jonex, Baxter & Khanduja (2013: 5), questionnaires are a very useful survey tool, allowing large populations to be assessed with relative ease.

The questionnaire employed contained 30 questions. In addition, semi-structured interviews with students were used to explore their perceptions and experiences of inquiry-based activities. The interview itself included eight open-ended questions appropriate for the purpose of this research. According to DeJonckheere & Vaughn (2019), semi-structured in-depth interviews are commonly used in qualitative research, and they are the most frequent qualitative data source in health service research.

4 Results

4.1 Quantitative Results

The survey on EFL teachers' perceptions of inquiry-based learning received responses from 32 teachers at the South East European University. However, only 30 surveys were filled out completely. The results are presented in Table 1 and Table 2:

Items		Agree	Neutral	Disagree
1	I look forward to lessons that use inquiry-based activities.	22	4	4
2	Inquiry-based activities are time consuming.	19	2	9
3	It is difficult to maintain control during inquiry-based activities in the class.	7	6	17
4	Language skills are the ability to ask and answer questions about real-life situations.	20	2	8
5	Inquiry work serves no purpose if learners do not use everyday English.	11	7	12
6	Language learning involves discovering new things about the world.	19	0	11
7	I prefer my learners to design their own inquiry activities.	17	5	8
8	Inquiry-based tasks help my learners to develop their problem solving skills.	26	1	3
9	I found online materials for inquiry-based lessons.	20	0	10
10	Assessment of inquiry-based activities is challenging.	23	1	7

Table 2: Teachers' Perception of inquiry-based learning

Based on the findings presented in Table 2, it can be concluded that teachers

generally hold positive perceptions of inquiry-based learning. The majority of participants, comprising 22 out of 30 teachers (73.3%), expressed enthusiasm for lessons that incorporated inquiry-based activities. While a small number of teachers, 7 out of 30 (23.3%), found maintaining class control to be a challenge, the overwhelming majority, 26 out of 30 (86.6%) agreed that inquiry-based learning developed problem-solving skills in their students.

Furthermore, the results indicate that a significant number of teachers, 23 out of 30 (76.6%), perceived assessment of inquiry-based learning to be challenging, suggesting a need for further development in this area. Regarding the availability of materials for inquiry-based classes, the majority of participants (20 out of 30; 66.6%) reported finding online materials useful, while one third of them, representing 10 teachers (33.3%), disagreed with this estimation.

Overall, these findings highlight the positive stance of teachers towards inquiry-based learning, with acknowledgment of its benefits for student learning outcomes. However, they also underscore certain challenges such as classroom management and assessment, indicating areas for potential improvement and professional development:

	Items	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
11	Students enjoy doing inquiry-based activities.	21	3	6
12	Students know how to identify problems during and give solutions in inquiry-based activities.	17	4	9
13	Inquiry-based activities improve students' communication skills.	28	1	1
14	Inquiry-based activities increase students' motivation for learning.	18	2	10
15	I have learners working in groups during inquiry-based activities and benefit from it.	17	4	9
16	Introverted students gladly participate in inquiry-based activities.	10	10	10
17	Students improve their critical thinking skills during inquiry-based learning.	18	5	7
18	Students are actively engaged during inquiry-based tasks.	26	1	3
19	Students' enjoyment is high in inquiry-based learning.	14	6	10
20	Students are highly concentrated while doing inquiries.	22	0	8

Table 3: Usefulness of Inquiry-based Learning Activities with Students

The findings presented in Table 3 indicate that teachers generally perceived inquiry-based learning activities as highly beneficial for students. More specifically, a majority of teachers, 28 out of 30 (93.3%), reported that inquiry-based learning activities were very useful for improving students' communication skills. Similarly, 26 teachers (86.6%) noted that students were actively engaged while working on inquiry-based activities, thus indicating a high level of commitment to learning. Teachers also observed that students enjoyed inquiry-based activities, with 21 (71%) out of 30 teachers reporting this finding. Furthermore, 22 (73.3%) teachers indicated that students demonstrated high levels of concentration when engaged in inquiry-based activities. However, there were mixed responses regarding the participation of introverted students in inquiry-based activities, where 10 (33.3%) teachers agreed that introverted students willingly participated in inquiry-based activities, another 10 teachers (33.3%) remained neutral on this statement, and 10 teachers (33.3%) disagreed with the notion that introverted students gladly participated in inquiry-based activities.

Overall, these findings suggest that teachers perceived inquiry-based activities as highly useful for students, particularly in terms of improving communication skills, increasing engagement, enjoyment, and concentration. However, there appears to be variability in how introverted students engaged with such activities, with some teachers observing willingness to participate while others did not.

4.2 Interview Results

The second instrument of this study involved interviews with 40 English as Foreign Language (EFL) students majoring in English Language and Literature. The purpose of the interviews was to inquire about the participants' experiences with inquiry-based learning within their department. The interview contained eight questions covering students' familiarity with IBL, their experiences, perceptions, benefits, challenges and possible recommendations for teachers while implementing IBL in the classroom. The participants who were interviewed were all students in the aforementioned department.

Q1: Do you know what inquiry-based learning is?

- P1: Yes, it is a new teaching approach related to problem-solving activities.
- P3: Well, it is a student-centred learning process which focuses on solving open-ended questions.
- P11: I think it is learning with the help of asking questions.
- P19: This approach makes students engaged in the learning process by making real-world connections through exploration.
- P22: I think it aims to encourage students to ask questions and find solutions to problems in real-life situations.

Analysing all the responses to the first question "Do you know what inquiry-based learning is?", it is collectively described as a student-centred teaching approach that emphasises problem solving and questioning. Key aspects include engaging students through exploration, focusing on open-ended questions, and making real-world

connections to encourage students to find solutions to real-world problems.

Q2: Can you describe your experience in using inquiry-based learning as positive or negative in the classroom?

- P5: Inquiry-based learning always works with students in a positive way because when you teach a hard topic, you connect it with some examples from real life.
- P15: One instance where I found inquiry-based learning to be very positive was during a group project. Our task was to research and present on a topic related to our studies. Instead of just assigning us a topic, the teacher allowed us to choose our own topics and encouraged us to explore our interests.
- P26: As a student, my experience with inquiry-based learning in the classroom has been overwhelmingly positive. It has transformed the way I approach learning and has had a significant impact on my educational journey.
- P27: Through inquiry-based learning, I have developed strong critical thinking and problem-solving skills. I have learned how to analyse information, evaluate its credibility, and draw logical conclusions.

Based on the responses to the question about participants' experiences with IBL, they generally indicated that inquiry-based learning was viewed positively, with benefits including increased engagement, autonomy, critical thinking and real-world connections. Specific examples (such as P15's group project) and detailed outcomes (such as P27's skills development) provided concrete evidence of its positive impact.

Q3: Do you think you achieved your learning aim(s)?

- P4: Personally, I think I have achieved my learning aims.
- P10: Yes, I strongly believe that my learning aims have been achieved.
- P28: Yes, because I have developed critical thinking skills and communication skills a lot.
- P39: I have because I am an introverted person and group work helped me to participate more in the problem we were given by the teacher.

An analysis of the responses to the question of whether students had achieved their learning objectives through IBL shows that the responses indicated a positive perception of the achievement of learning objectives, with varying levels of detail. P28 and P39 provided more detailed insights by specifying skills acquired and personal growth experiences, whereas P4 and P10 provided more general affirmations of their achievements.

Q4: Can you name any factors of inquiry-based learning you find the most / least useful?

- P7: Factors of inquiry-based learning that I often found useful are: curiosity and engagement, independence and autonomy. While least useful was the need for guidance.
- P14: For the most useful I would choose the problem-based inquiry approach when you give students a real life problem and they with their problem-solving skills need to solve the problem and the least effective I would choose the lecture method or the oral method of teaching.

- P27: Some factors that make inquiry-based learning useful include active student engagement and collaborative learning. On the other hand, some factors that may make inquiry-based learning less useful include teacher preparation and prior knowledge.
- P34: The most useful factors of inquiry-based learning are a context for questions, a framework for questions, a focus for questions and different levels of questions. Least useful would be evaluation of the activity.

Based on the interview responses regarding the most and least useful factors of IBL, the participants mentioned curiosity, engagement, problem solving skills and collaboration. On the other hand, the need for guidance, method of teaching / lecturing, teacher preparation and evaluation of the activity were mentioned as the least useful.

Q5: What was the most challenging in inquiry-based learning?

- P14: I needed to be trained to practise inquiry-based activities in the class.
- P20: For me, the most challenging aspect was to solve problems but luckily we worked in groups so we managed it very well.
- P 31: Students' preparedness because it is a time-consuming activity.

An analysis of the responses to the challenges that inquiry-based learning posed for pupils revealed the need for adequate teacher training, the difficulty of the problem-solving tasks and the need for pupils to be well prepared due to the time-consuming nature of these activities. These findings point to the importance of professional development for teachers, the benefits of collaborative learning, and the need for effective time management and preparation.

Q6: Which courses encouraged the use of inquiry-based learning?

- P2: For me, this was more appropriate to be used in language skills classes because I was given freedom to work.
- P17: In the course ESP for law, we were thrilled to work on inquiry-based tasks because it helped us to solve problems related to law.
- P29: Inquiry-based learning was very useful for us while taking a teaching methodology-related course because we could choose our own activities for class presentations.
- P34: Definitely the course language and society encouraged the use of inquiry-based activities in class.

When asked about the courses that most promoted IBL in the classroom, participants identified Language Skills, ESP for Law, Teaching Methodology and the Language and Society course.

Q7: Do you have any suggestions for teachers for inquiry-based learning?

- P1: My suggestion is to practise it with the students because it increases our critical thinking skills.
- P9: My experience with inquiry-based learning was very useful therefore, I strongly recommend it to teachers of EFL.
- P12: I would suggest they implement it in class especially for developing collaboration

and speaking skills of the students.

P22: I would definitely suggest it to teachers because it encouraged active learning where we actively participated in the learning process through inquiry-based activities.

In response to question 7, which asked for any other suggestions for teachers, the students indicated that they were all in favour of implementing IBL in the classroom because it improved their critical thinking, developed collaboration in the classroom and promoted active learning. In general, the students' suggestions highlighted the many benefits of implementing inquiry-based learning in the classroom, and their feedback emphasised the importance of incorporating inquiry-based approaches into teaching practices in order to create engaging and effective learning experiences for all students.

Q8: Will you use it when you become a teacher? Why or why not?

P5: I will definitely use it with my students in my future teaching career.

P28: Yes, I think I will use it to develop my students' critical thinking skills.

P35: I will think about it when I become a teacher.

P40: Yes, because I really enjoyed the group work and problems we had to solve.

When asked about their use of IBL once they become teachers, participants recognised the potential benefits of IBL in promoting critical thinking, collaboration and engagement. Positive experiences with IBL activities such as group work and problem solving also influenced participants' intentions to use them in their future teaching careers.

The overall results from the students' interviews indicate a strong preference for inquiry-based learning as their favourite class activity, with universally positive and rewarding experiences reported by all participants. Although it can be suggested that interview responses may be influenced by the research process, the genuine enthusiasm of students for Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) is evident in classrooms where researchers have implemented it themselves.

The above findings underscore the effectiveness of inquiry-based approaches in engaging students and fostering a supportive and enriching learning environment. They suggest that inquiry-based learning resonates well with students, improves their critical thinking skills and contributes to their overall satisfaction with the course. It also helped them to learn how to analyse information, evaluate its credibility, and draw logical conclusions as well as work collaboratively.

5 Limitations of the Study

During the research process, the researchers encountered several limitations. These included a small pool of participants drawn exclusively from one institution, as well as limitations related to research methods and insufficient training for teachers in the implementation of Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) in the classroom.

A limited number of participants undermines the representativeness of the study's findings and hinders the ability to draw broader conclusions. This limitation can result in a lack of diverse perspectives, experiences and contextual factors, which may lead to biased or distorted findings. As a result, the findings may lack robustness and may not accurately reflect the different experiences and challenges associated with IBL in different educational settings.

Furthermore, the lack of a survey method limits the systematic collection and analysis of quantitative data on participants' perceptions, attitudes and behaviours towards IBL. Surveys could provide standardised measures of the depth of participants' experience of IBL, their level of satisfaction and their perceptions of its effectiveness. Without survey data, the study relies heavily on qualitative data, interviews, which, while insightful, may not provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under study.

In addition, inadequate teacher training in the implementation of IBL can lead to inconsistent or ineffective implementation practices. This deficiency may impede teachers' ability to effectively facilitate inquiry-based activities, resulting in suboptimal learning experiences for students. Inadequate training may also contribute to challenges such as difficulties in designing meaningful inquiry tasks, managing group dynamics, or accurately assessing student learning outcomes.

6 Conclusions

The present study was designed to explore teachers and students' perceptions of inquiry-based learning at the tertiary level of education. The implementation of this approach in teaching EFL has been found to have several benefits including the development of communications skills, collaboration among students, the development of critical thinking, and active learning. These benefits contribute to a more engaging, effective, and enriching educational experience both for teachers and students.

Teachers' responses to the quantitative part of the survey underscored their positive attitude towards inquiry-based learning, with recognition of its benefits for student learning outcomes. However, they also highlighted certain challenges, such as classroom management and assessment, that warrant attention and potential areas for improvement through professional development initiatives. These findings answer the first research questions about teachers' perceptions of inquiry-based learning at the tertiary level.

In response to the second research questions on students' attitudes and experiences with inquiry-based learning in the classroom, the results were also very positive. Students reported that they were familiar that this approach is a student-centred learning process which focuses on solving open-ended questions and makes students engaged in the learning process by establishing real-world connections through exploration. The most useful factors during its' implementation were curiosity and engagement on the students' part as well as independence and autonomy. However, students still needed guidance throughout the learning process. The least useful factors influencing IBL implementation were teacher preparation and prior knowledge, and evaluation of learning activities. Finally, the inquiry-based activities were most

useful for courses in language skills, English for specific purposes, and language methodology.

In response to the third research question on the benefits of implementing inquiry-based learning in the EFL classroom, both groups, i.e. teachers and students, perceived inquiry-based activities as highly beneficial for students, particularly in enhancing communication skills, increasing engagement, enjoyment, and concentration on the tasks to be performed. These positive perceptions reflected the effectiveness of inquiry-based learning in promoting active student involvement and fostering a conducive learning environment.

However, there was a slight variability in how introverted students engaged with inquiry-based activities. While some teachers observed that introverted students willingly participated in such activities, others did not report the same level of participation. This discrepancy highlighted the importance of considering individual student needs and preferences when implementing inquiry-based approaches. It underscored the need for educators to adopt strategies that accommodate diverse learning styles and personalities, thus ensuring that all students can fully engage and benefit from inquiry-based learning experiences.

All in all, this study has contributed valuable insights into the perceptions and experiences of both teachers and students regarding inquiry-based learning at the tertiary level. It has highlighted the positive impact of inquiry-based approaches on student learning outcomes and emphasised the importance of addressing challenges to further enhance the effectiveness of this instructional method.

It is strongly recommended that further research and professional development initiatives be undertaken to address challenges such as classroom management, assessment, and the engagement of introverted students. In addition, the study suggests the need for ongoing support and training for teachers to effectively implement inquiry-based learning strategies and to maximise the benefits of inquiry-based learning in the EFL classroom, not only in North Macedonia, but also beyond.

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